

Cleaning pure sinusoids

Adolf Cusmariu
adolcus@gmail.com

Let's start with one digital cycle of the sinusoid $s = \sin(x)$, at rate $r=.001$; thus

```
r=.001;  
x=0:r:2*pi;  
len=length(x);  
s=sin(x);
```

It seems too simple to work, but double integration via the OCTAVE 'cumsum' command should recover $\sin(x)$, with some numerical error.

Here's the code:

```
cs=1-cumsum(r*s); % Integration to cos(x); '1' is the constant of integration  
css=cumsum(r*cs); % Integration back to sin(x); constant of integration now is '0'
```

Results are plotted below (left-to-right): the digital s , cs , css

The error $\{s - css\}$ has dispersion, $\text{std}(s-css) = 7.0721e-04$.

Let's try this with a noisy sinusoid; integration is a smoother, so noise reduction should follow through this 'double cleaning'. Here's the OCTAVE output.

```
ns=randn(size(s)); % GWN  
sn=s+ns; % Add noise
```

In the graphic below (left-to-right): the original sinusoid $\{s\}$, Gaussian White Noise $\{ns\}$, and lastly $\{s + ns\}$. The noisy sinusoid seems hopeless to clean up!

Let's try it anyway; in OCTAVE code:

```
csn=1-cumsum(r*sn); % Integration of noisy sin(x) to cos(x)  
cssn=cumsum(r*cssn); % Integration back to sin(x)
```

Results are plotted below; (left-to-right): the 'clean' sinusoid {cssn}, the removed noise {cssn - sn}, and the difference {s - cssn} between the original sinusoid and the 'clean' version through 'double smoothing'.

Error dispersion relative to the original sinusoid is $\text{std}(s-\text{cssn}) = 0.023522$.

Let's try next adding uniformly-distributed noise, made zero-mean first. Thus

```
ns=rand(size(s)); % Uniform Noise  
ns=ns-mean(ns); % Zero-mean UN  
sn=s+ns; % Add ZUN
```

The sinusoid, ZUN, and their sum are shown below.

The 'double cleaning' operation produced again excellent results; see below, displayed left-to-right as 'clean' sinusoid, extracted noise, and the estimation error, with dispersion $\text{std}(s-\text{cssn}) = 0.0085926$.

Multiplicative noise cleaning requires a bit more care, but the above method still works. The noise needs to be normalized in range to (0, 1); while this range holds for Uniform Noise UN ('rand(.)' in OCTAVE), Gaussian White Noise GWN ('randn(.)') is normalized as

$$NGWN = (GWN - \min(GWN))/\text{range}(GWN)$$

Let's just work the GWN case in OCTAVE code, using the same sinusoid.

```
r=.001;
x=0:r:2*pi;
len=length(x);
s=sin(x);

ns=randn(size(s)); % GWN
ns=(ns-min(ns))/range(ns); % Normalization

sn=s.*ns; % Multiplicative noise
```


The figure above shows $\{s\}$, $\{ns\}$, and $\{s*ns\}$. Noise removal follows the same path; however, some (admittedly ad hoc) adjustments are needed. First, the re-scaling

```
cn=cumsum(r*sn);
cn=cn/max(cn);
```

Then

```
csn=1-2*cn;
```

will yield $\cos(x)$, ready for the final integration:

$cssn=cumsum(r*csn)$; in the display below (left-to-right) is the 'clean' sinusoid, the extracted noise, and the error relative to the input, with dispersion $\text{std}(s-cssn)=.0015741$.

